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Psycho-Affective Factors Influencing the Oral Performance of Third Year High School Students of MSU-Taraka Agricultural Extension College

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Abstract.

No single major problem can be pinpointed to account for the dismal record of the performance of Philippine students, particularly high school students, for a complex of problems has long been known to plague the educational system – e.g., inadequate resources that spawn chronic classroom shortage, teacher shortage and lack of training, student-teacher ratio, poor facilities, etc. Given less attention are psycho-affective factors that impact the student-teacher relationship and student oral performance. These should not be ignored, considering the fact that learning in an ESL setting is basically a student-teacher interaction or engagement. This descriptive qualitative-quantitative study addresses this lacuna by inquiring into the influence of psycho affective factors on the oral performance of third-year high school students of MSU-Taraka Agricultural College Extension in the hope that the findings could serve as a guide for crafting a form of intervention or supplemental services to help develop oral skills before these students enter college. Data were obtained through a self-constructed questionnaire to secure the demographic profile of the 53 respondents, comprising two intact sections: the Personality Type Test, adapted from the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator, and an oral test. For purposes of triangulation, observation was also done. The inquiry revealed that most of the respondents were vulnerable to anxiety attacks before and during a class presentation; they lacked strong motivation and were inhibited by low self-esteem. They found oral activity more difficult than other skills and felt nervous performing in front of the class. It is, however, noteworthy that the hypothesis testing did not reveal any positive relationship between the psycho-affective factors considered as intervening variables, namely anxiety, motivation and self-esteem, and their oral performance, indicating that other psycho-affective factors and, possibly, some social factors, may prove significant or salient vis-à-vis oral performance. In light of the ambiguous and less than satisfactory results, the researcher deems it necessary to hazard a possible cause: the significantly reduced number of respondents, from 53 to 28, who participated throughout the inquiry. She believed that a larger sample could have yielded a different, clearer pattern or picture.

Keywords: Psycho-affective Factor, Affective Filter, Oral Performance, Humanistic Pedagogy, Facilitative Tension and Debilitating Tension

1.0 Introduction

The performance of Philippine students, particularly high school students, has been a cause for perturbation for over two decades now, but concern regarding this has never been more compelling and pressing. As laid bare in the recent EDCOM II report, proficiency of high school students has precipitously dropped from 30% to 0.47% by the time they graduate and enter college (Kee, November

2025). A complex of problems, already acknowledged as perennial and chronic, has plagued the educational system for a long time. Problems at the macro level – i.e., inadequate resources that spawn classroom shortage, congestion and bloated classes in violation of the accepted class size, teacher shortage and lack of training, deplorable student-teacher ratio, and lack of facilities vital to a supportive learning environment, such as library and laboratories. The poor quality, low proficiency and inequity that characterize the Philippine educational system have ineluctably created a learning crisis. This is lamentable as the problem has a deleterious effect on the development of human capital, a crucial component of national progress.

Raucous public outcry about the foregoing problems at the macro level drowns out lament about micro level problems like classroom management and pedagogical issues and student-teacher interaction or engagement, particularly in an ESL setting where oral performance or production is decisive, that is, used as a measure of student learning. ESL students' litany of woes includes debilitating tension or nervousness, fear of making mistakes and being laughed at and drawing harsh remarks from the teacher, loss of self-confidence, and deflated ego. In an ESL classroom, these are commonplace as attempts to use English as a second language require great effort and daring for many in socio-cultural backwaters like Taraka. Oral production is more challenging than other classroom activities because it puts a student on the spot, or under the critical lens of both fellow students and teachers. As Krashen (1981) and Burt & Dulay, 1978; 1982) explain, the socio-affective filter is likely to be activated, hindering the learner from making use of input, or blocking the input from reaching the "black box", a metaphor for the mechanism in the brain that processes input so that it becomes meaningful learning through subsumption, to borrow the term used by Ausubel in his theory of cognitive learning; this means new material to learn is related and anchored to relevant established entities in the cognitive structure. This cognitive structure is conceived as a system of building blocks. As fully enunciated by Krashen in his Input Hypothesis, the less anxious the learner is, the better learning proceeds; relaxed students can learn more in shorter periods of time.

There is voluminous literature on the proper environment and approach or methodology for learning using English as a Second Language. David Nunan (1989), a leading light in the Communicative Approach, echoes Krashen in asserting that students learn better in a supportive, embracing, non-threatening environment. Among methods that give special emphasis on making the learning environment as comfortable as possible by reducing tension are the so-called "designers' methods of the 70's, namely, Lozanov's Suggestopedia or Suggestology, Curran's Community Language Learning and Gattegno's Silent Way (Brown, 2000; Stevick, 1996; Richards & Rodgers, 1986; Ovando & Collier, 1985). Offering itself as a foundation for humanistic education or pedagogy is Carl Rogers' humanistic psychology (Brown, 2000), which propounds the principle that the individual/learner is a "fully functioning" or "whole person," thus in a way warning against ignoring "feelings" or the affective dimension of learning. Rogers' position has important implications for education. It shifts the focus away from teaching to learning. The goal of education is the facilitation of change and learning. Learning how to learn is more important than being "taught" something from the superior vantage point of a teacher who unilaterally decides what should be taught. In this context, the existing system of education, in which the teacher dictates what shall be learned, denies the student freedom and dignity.

This inquiry was pursued to help redress the imbalance in addressing the learning crisis, which tends to relegate to the background problems "closer to the hearth" the classroom as a vital center of learning, directly involving students and teachers. While it is true that the macro-level problems mentioned do have an effect on the learning outcome, the effect of psycho-affective factors on the learning process itself can hardly be exaggerated. This study set out with the assumption that oral performance/production is subject to the influence of the student's demographic profile, which provides information on their background or provenance, and psycho-affective factors identified and

isolated by the researcher for investigation.

The researcher believes that psycho-affective factors come to the fore in oral performance rendered in English as a second language. The challenge is greater for students in rural areas where English is treated as more of a foreign language than a second language and is rarely used, resulting in limited English proficiency. Added to these is that speaking, as a productive skill, compared to writing, another productive skill, and the receptive skills, demands more of students. Usually put to the test through oral performance, oral skill, or proficiency makes a complicated matter, involving both declarative and procedural knowledge. As explained by Stevick (1996), “declarative” is used for whatever contents of memory are “articulable”, that is, for whatever facts or relationships can be or could be transmitted through words; it is sometimes called “propositional knowledge”. In contrast, procedural knowledge is made up of multiple productions; it involves “doing”.

Research Questions

To frame and guide the inquiry, the following questions were formulated:

1. What is the respondent’s profile in terms of :
 - 1.1 gender
 - 1.2 socio-economic status?
2. What personality/character types do the respondents possess?
3. What psycho-affective factors are facilitative in the oral performance of the respondents?
4. What psycho-affective factors are debilitating in the oral performance of the respondents?

This focus on the gamut of emotions (“affects”) that students experience in oral performance should generate valuable information that can serve as a prod to teachers’ reflection and self-examination. How aware are they of psycho-affective factors that could affect students’ oral production or performance? Have they been sensitive enough to psycho-affective factors at work when they require oral performance of their students? Discoveries they make about their students’ personality/character and how psycho-affective factors influence their oral performance could awaken them to recognize the latter’s idiosyncratic and diverse needs and interact with them in more humane and meaningful ways. Such realization is a powerful impetus for them to try out new approaches, methods or strategies to eliminate, or at least, reduce the deleterious effect of psycho-affective factors on students’ oral performance.

2.0 Methodology

This study was conducted as a mixed methods research, employing aspects of both qualitative and quantitative procedures. Involving the use of both forms or approaches, the overall strength of this kind of study is greater than either qualitative or quantitative research alone, neutralizing the limitations of each (Cresswell,2009).

2.1 Research Design

The mixed methods research was deemed most apt and proper for the stated objectives of the study, which require making some determinations, specifically the demographic profile of the respondents and their personality/character types, as well as assessing their performance on the Oral Test conducted. These procedures produce quantitative data. To find support or substantiation for the results of the analysis made of said body of data, interviews with the respondents were conducted. Observation, a more unobtrusive data gathering method which entails systematic noting and recording of classroom behavior, particularly during an oral performance and the sit-in or auditing, was also done. This method is thought productive, that is, based on the assumption that behavior is expressive of feelings, attitudes, and beliefs. Individual interviews tend to have an inhibitory effect on

the respondents; hence, the need for the data obtained by this means to be augmented, balanced, and checked against data gathered by more observations. The latter, also used for purposes of triangulation, is very productive of field notes.

2.2 Research Locale and Participants

The inquiry was conducted at MSU-Taraka Agricultural Extension College in Mangayao, Taraka, First District of Lanao del Sur. Taraka is located in the area of the province commonly referred to as Basak, meaning lowland, in the eastern part of Lake Lanao. The research site is one of the fifteen “feeder schools” of the Mindanao State University, which means the high school graduates of these schools are expected to qualify for admission to college work at the MSU, based on their SASE scores. MSU-Taraka Agricultural Extension College is under the supervision of the Assistant Vice Chancellor for Academic Affairs, who provides general oversight to all the MSU Community High Schools. The said office was created to extend the geographic reach of the service and influence of the MSU to other Muslim groups like the Maguindanaons and Taosugs, and non-Muslim groups or Indigenous Peoples (Lumads) of the Zamboanga Peninsula, Davao, Cotabato and other parts of MINSUPALA.

The study set out with a sample of fifty-five third-year students comprising two intact sections: Section Pilot, 30 and Section B, 25. This group of junior students was chosen because of the “critical period” in which the researcher expected to find them; “critical” because of their chronological age that warrants some expectations, specifically being still trainable in terms of language learning and at the same time, could be credited with enough maturity to understand instructions and determination to complete their high school education to proceed to the tertiary level. Related to these considerations is the hope that in their remaining time in high school, they could still benefit from whatever form of intervention or supplemental service may be devised or crafted to help enhance their oral skills.

2.3 Research Instruments

The following instruments were used to gather data desired for the inquiry:

1. Questionnaire. This researcher-designed questionnaire was utilized to obtain personal data deemed to have a bearing on the shaping of their personality/ character type, which in turn, influences their oral performance: gender and socio-economic status of the family (based on educational attainment and income of the parents, and appliances at home).

2. Personality/Character Type Indicator Test. Adapted from the Myers-Briggs Inventory Model, this typing was required of all the respondents. It covers four pairs of categories: extroversion-introversion, sensing-intuition, thinking, feeling, and judging-perceiving. There is a list of statement indicators for each pair of categories.

3. Oral Test. This oral test was in the form of an oral performance, which was required of all respondents. Performance was to be evaluated by three raters.

4. Interview Schedule. Individual or one-on-one interviews with the respondents were conducted to allow the researcher to do gentle or sensitive probing of the feelings or affective dimension of learning through a few guide question framed. The personal interaction and cooperation involved allow immediate follow-up and clarification. While the intent is to draw as much revealing information from the participant, the researcher should remain in control so as to prevent digression or overly long narratives.

5. Observation. A more unobtrusive data-gathering technique, observation is usually combined with an interview to counter or minimize the limitations of face- to-face interview which usually cause discomfort on the part of interviewees, especially students who may also be unwilling

to share information about their feelings or attitudes, and may even have good reasons to be less truthful. The researcher took on the role of an unobtrusive observer and recorder. Observation in this study served a very important purpose: triangulation.

2.4 Data Gathering Procedure

Protocols governing the conduct of data gathering were conscientiously observed. These included securing official permission from the Principal of MSU-Taraka Agricultural Extension College and holding an orientation with the teachers of the two sections of third-year high school students who made up the sample of the study. The said orientation was considered vital to ensure the cooperation of both teachers and students and coordination between them and the researcher, so that necessary adjustments in the schedules of the concerned teachers could be made. These were observed to the end of minimizing disruption of planned classroom activities. Data gathering, including interviews and observation, took two months. It was done in several phases:

1. Questionnaire and Personality/Character Type Administration. To maximize the time allotted for this, both forms were passed out in each class on the same day, and simultaneously, by the researcher herself, with the concerned teachers assisting. The participants were allowed to bring home the forms to give them enough time to answer the questionnaires and were instructed to return the completed survey forms the following day. The forms were retrieved or received from the concerned teachers.
2. Oral Presentation. This crucial activity was scheduled a week later, again with the help of the concerned teachers. This was required of all 55 participants to assess their current status or level of proficiency/oral skills as students using ESL in an oral performance. Their performance was to be evaluated by three raters from the Department of English of the College of Social Sciences and Humanities, MSU. Each rater had at least five years of teaching English behind her. On learning that outsiders would rate their performance, many of the participants had panic attacks. They refused to participate further despite the efforts of both concerned teachers to reassure them that the outcome would not be taken into account in the computation of their final grades and that its use would be restricted to the inquiry underway. Moreover, the findings of the study could lead to the development of a form of intervention and supplemental service to help enhance their oral skills.
3. An interview, more in the form of an informal conversation, but guided by a few questions, was held with a small number of the remaining participants who agreed to take part in a 15-minute casual talk with this researcher—a single session during recess or a break sufficed to avoid encroaching further on class time.
4. This phase of the inquiry did not require a separate schedule. The researcher took note of the classroom behavior of the students, particularly their interaction with their classmates and with their teacher. Administering the questionnaires and the Oral Presentation gave her a vantage point to observe their classroom behavior objectively and unobtrusively. Moreover, she spent enough time to “sit in” in both sections, making her presence as inconspicuous as possible by sitting at the back. At the orientation for the concerned teachers, she sought and secured the informed consent and cooperation of the former for the planned classroom ethnography.

Throughout the conduct of the data-gathering part of the inquiry, from the orientation for the concerned teachers and the administration of the questionnaires to the Oral Presentations, sit-ins and interviews, a recording machine was used to ensure accurate transcription. Photos were taken with the knowledge and consent of the concerned teachers and their students.

2.5 Ethical Considerations.

The inquiry was undertaken with utmost care and attention to ethical principles and established research protocols.

1. Securing official permission in the form of a formal written request to conduct the inquiry at the identified research site. A schedule of the data gathering phases was attached.
2. Informed consent. The researcher held an orientation or meeting with the teachers of the two intact sections – Section Pilot and Section B – to introduce herself and explain to them the objectives of the study and the need for their cooperation and assistance. A detailed account or description of the data gathering procedure and the crucial part the respective teachers of the two intact sections would play in ensuring the success of the inquiry took up the better part of the orientation. They were encouraged to raise questions or seek clarification about the schedules of the activities involving their cooperation and assistance, in particular, the oral presentation and the series of observations, and what was expected of them. The meeting with the teachers was done, and their informed consent secured, the researcher was introduced to each of their respective sections. The researcher briefly discussed in each class the purpose of the study, explaining how the findings or results would benefit them, and appealed for their willingness, full cooperation and serious participation in the endeavor.
3. Confidentiality of information and anonymity of the participants. Information obtained from the participants was treated with confidentiality. Their privacy and identity were protected by the anonymity assurance. In referring to them in the analysis or report, a set of symbols – e.g., Student A, Student X, and the like –or pseudonyms- may be used.
4. In view of the somewhat longer time the data gathering would take (two months) and the long-term relationship or interactions this entailed, the researcher did her best not only to establish rapport with the concerned teachers and their students, but also to forge a bond of trust with them by freely mingling with them every chance she got.

2.6 Validity and Reliability

In view of the simplicity of the researcher-designed questionnaire used to obtain personal information from the participants, with only a few basic items included, a trial or pilot testing was not considered necessary. Only the Personality/Character Type (adapted from the Myers-Briggs Inventory Model), given the list of statement indicators for each pair of categories – e.g., extroversion-introversion – had to be subjected to the procedure to ensure its comprehensibility and clarity to the study's participants. To ensure and increase the validity of data, triangulation was observed through the use of various data gathering instruments and methods, types of data and theories. This allowed the comparison of data from different sources or by different methods, thus improving the accuracy of findings.

3.0 Results and Discussion

This section is devoted to the analysis and interpretation of the collected data and the resulting findings. These are discussed according to the sequence set in the presentation of the research questions.

3.1 Profile of the Student-Participants

The first question is concerned with personal data, specifically gender, socio-economic background or status, and personality/character types deemed to have saliency for the problem under consideration.

3.1.1 Gender

As shown in Table 1, a huge majority of the final sample of twenty-eight (28) were female (21 or 75%) and only 7 (25%) were male. The girls outnumbered the boys by well over 50%.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	21	75.00%
Male	7	25%
TOTAL	28	100.00%

The numerical dominance of females in education is an observed constant as borne out by numerous studies in the past two decade like those of Varquez (2013), Hadji Nasser (2013), Mangoranda (2012), Cruda (2012), Domato (2012), Genon-Sieras (2011) and Tan (2011). The educational sector is overrun by females. Females forming a statistical majority is an acknowledged worldwide phenomenon, in fact.

Studies that touched on the wide female-male ratio in schools focused on various concerns: sexually-determined neurophysiological differences between males and females (Maccoby & Jacklin, 1974; cited in McKeever, 1988) which presented data showing females to be superior to males in at least some aspects of language ability; greater bilaterality of language processing and execution in females (Levy, 1969); correlation between sex and hemispheric specialization. Regarding language and sex, in particular, there exist studies that suggest that “girls begin to speak earlier than boys. . .express themselves more frequently. . .show earlier use of two-word sentences. . .and develop a larger vocabulary at an early age” (and thus support the proposal that hemispheric specialization for some tasks occurs earlier in females than in males (Shucard, Shucard, and Thomas; cited in (Steele, 1988).

Many aspects of the academic life of students have been examined to discover how similar or different boys and girls are (Crawford & Unger, 2000; Santrock, 2004). Some differences in their math and science skills, verbal skills, educational attainment, relationship skills, and aggression and self-regulation have surfaced. In regard to verbal skills, girls tend to have better skills than boys, outperforming their male counterparts in reading and writing in the elementary and secondary school years. In recent national studies, females had higher reading achievement than males in 4, 8 and 12, with the gap widening as students progressed through school (Coley, 2001).

Gender was singled out from a host of personal data not only because it has been repeatedly shown to make a difference in language learning that involves oral production, but also because of the recognized difference in the psychological make-up of males and females. Sprinthall et al. (1998), Craig (1992) and Kelly (1985), cited in Amer (2013), are among those who made assertions that gender could account for differences among individuals. It has been posited that boys generally perform better than girls in mathematics and science subjects/courses, but girls excel in language arts, spelling, and vocabulary. Although some of the other claims made may be stereotypical, they could not be dismissed outright as completely baseless. For example, boys are usually depicted as more aggressive, uninhibited, and imperturbable, and are more likely to take risks. In contrast, girls are more susceptible to self-consciousness, apprehensions, anxiety and the like. It seems safe to say, or to accept as a truism, that girls are different from boys, and vice versa.

There is thus a basis for the assumption that their behavior, attitudes and reactions to an oral presentation differ.

3.1.2 Socio-economic Status

Educational Attainment of Respondents' Parents (Fathers and Mothers)

Socio-economic background is assumed to have relevance for the psycho-affective aspect of

students' language learning, particularly their oral performance, as highlighted in various studies such as those of Coleman and Karwit (1970; cited in (Flores, 1992 and Domato, 2012). Among the family's socio-economic variables to which importance is ascribed is the parents' educational attainment.

As a comparison of the data Tables 2.A and 2.B provide on the educational attainment of the participants' fathers and the mothers; there are more college graduates among mother (11 or 39.29%) than the fathers (5 or 17.88%). The rest in each group had gone only as far as high school or elementary school. Taraka, being a rural area, the result does not come as a surprise. The study of Tocalo (2012) on the reading comprehension level of Grade 6 students in Maguing, another rural area, had a similar setup in terms of parents' educational attainment.

Table 2.A. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents' Fathers by Educational Attainment*

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary Graduate	10	35.71%
High School Graduate	8	28.57%
College Level	5	17.86%
College Graduate	5	17.86%
TOTAL	28	100.00%

Table 2.B. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents' Mothers by Educational Attainment*

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
College Graduate	11	39.29 %
Elementary Graduate	9	32.13 %
High School Graduate	5	17.86 %
College Level	3	10.71 %
TOTAL	28	100.00%

Although no significant relationship was discovered between respondents' socio-economic background and their positive attitudes and motivation in relation to language learning in Dital's study (2009), this cannot be put forward as the majority opinion or view. Numerous studies advanced opposed results or findings. For example, Sunggod's study (2010) on factors affecting the oral performance of students in the course Public Speaking (English 7) provided evidence that among such factors are mothers' education and occupation, in addition to the extent of exposure to public speaking.

A comparison of the data on the educational attainment of respondents' fathers with those found in recent studies, like that of Hadji Nasser (2013), reveals an interesting contrast. In the latter, the largest cluster was that of college graduates; elementary graduates formed the smallest group. Other fathers have at least reached the college level, and some are holders of Ph.Ds.. It should, however, be noted that the school covered in the study is a private establishment. Students attending the school come from relatively well-off families. Among the indicators of these families' socio-economic status are the parents' educational attainment. Thus, comparing the result of this study with that of Hadji Nasser's amounts to an invidious or unfair comparison.

The result of Tocalo's study (2012) on the English proficiency, focused on reading comprehension levels, of Grade Six students, which was conducted in the municipality of Maguing, is comparable with the present one. Elementary education was all the education received by a large number, almost 50% of the study's sample, in contrast to the 14% who were able to complete their college education. The number progressively decreased in the higher levels. It is easy to find the explanation for the similar results: the context or locale of the study. Both Taraka and Maguing are rural areas in which privations like lack of opportunities for education and livelihood are commonplace.

Social scientists have adequate grounds for linking parents' education to the academic achievement as well as character development of their children (Hurlock, 1979), cited in (Flores, 1992 and Domato, 2012). Parents play a persuasive role model to their children. Sons tend to hero-worship their fathers, but it is mothers who are recognized as primary caretakers and advocates of their children. What is clear is that students from disadvantaged homes find themselves at a disadvantage in school, and may even bring to class hang-ups, insecurities and complexes. On the other hand, students from privileged backgrounds feel confident about facing up to any challenge in school. In Astin (1971; cited in Domato, 2012), the level of education of the father and mother is an important factor affecting the achievement of students. Stenberg (1995) and Feldhussen and Hoover (1996), cited in Flores (1992), and Amer (2013), focused in their studies on the interfaces between the internal and external worlds of individuals. They propounded that the personal profile of a person impacts their daily activities. It thus follows that school performance may be determined to a considerable extent by his profile and the interplay of outside and inside forces.

Further, as pointed out by Hadji Nasser (2013), mothers are likely to make more assiduous or devoted tutors at home. Highly educated mothers more fully realize the importance of their involvement in the education of their children. Domato (2012) stressed this, sketching out the crucial role played by the mother as primary caretaker and principal stakeholder in their young's education - for example, monitoring their children's progress, providing supplementary service or assistance like tutoring, helping with the extra-class work, periodically consulting/conferencing with the teachers, and actively participating in the school's activities or programs.

However, in an adverse or negative but effective manner, Corpuz-Bendiyo (2012) showed in her case study involving preschoolers with or at risk for learning difficulties how mothers who do not have the time, patience and understanding could bungle or botch up the whole thing and aggravate, instead of ameliorating the situation. The stories of the three subjects featured in the inquiry serve as cautionary tales for mothers who abdicate their responsibility as primary caretakers or are remiss in guiding and supporting their young children through the initial paces of learning.

Occupation of Respondents' Parents. Considered as relevant and salient as parents' educational attainment is their occupation or profession, the data on this is shown in Table 3.A and 3. B. The participants' fathers are mostly farmers (50.00%) and businessmen (28,97%). A great majority of the mothers (71.43%) declared themselves as housewives, a result that leaves one wondering where the college graduates among them have gone.

Table 3.A. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents' Fathers by Occupation/Profession

Occupation/Profession	Frequency	Percentage
Farmer	14	50.00%
Businessman	8	28.57 %
L.T.O	1	3.57 %
Carpenter	1	3.57%
Merchandiser	1	3.57%
Driver	1	3.57%
Government Employee	1	3.57%
None	1	3.57%
TOTAL	28	100.00%

Table 3.B. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents' Mothers by Occupation/Profession

Occupation/Profession	Frequency	Percentage
Housewife	20	71.43%
Business	4	14.29%
Midwife	2	7.14%
Teacher	1	3.57%
Nurse/OFW	1	3.57%
TOTAL	28	100.00%

Farming as a common occupation among fathers vividly portrays the kind of life lived in the setting or community in which the study was conducted. Taraka is located in the Basak area, which is mostly farmland, and as some features of the place indicate, the overall atmosphere is rural and bucolic. The area is a veritable socio-cultural backwater. This is the typical situation in municipalities lying along the eastern part of Lake Lanao, as described also in Tocalo’s study (2012), which covered the municipality of Maguing. Farming is followed by business, which can be presumed to be a small-scale business or modest entrepreneurial ventures. Moreover, few qualify for stable occupations or professions like teaching, engineering, and government service. This finding is in accord with the data or findings concerning the fathers’ educational attainment, which reports a greater number of elementary graduates than college graduates.

What is discernible in the pattern revealed in Table 3. B above is the majority’s order of priorities. They take their role as mother and housewife seriously. More than fifty percent (20 who described themselves as “housewives” seem resigned to their “destined” place: the home as the center of their existence. Only three (3) of the mothers practice some profession – e.g., teaching, nursing, and midwifery – when eleven (11) or 39.294% are supposed to be college graduates. A plausible explanation suggests itself. Meranaw culture is patriarchal; in other words, male dominance is a given. Meranaw men tend to be tradition-bound in their thinking or attitude. They believe that the proper stage for women is the domestic sphere. They take pride in their role as breadwinners.

Parents’ Monthly Income. As set out in Tables 4.A and 4.B, the common average monthly income of both groups of parents is 4999 and below, followed by the 5000-9999 bracket. No one among the fathers declared receiving income in the 20,000 and above bracket. A few mothers, most likely those working as professionals and OFWs, registered higher incomes.

Table 4.A. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents’ Fathers by Monthly Income*

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
4,999 & below	17	60.71%
5,000 – 9,999	8	28.57%
10,000 – 14,999	2	7.14%
15,000 – 19,999	1	3.57%
20,000 & above	0	10.71%
TOTAL	28	100.00%

Table 4.B. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents’ Mothers by Monthly Income*

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
4,999 & below	22	78.57 %
5,000 – 9,999	1	3.57%
10,000 – 14,999	1	3.57%
15,000 – 19,999	1	3.57%
20,000 & above	3	10.71%
TOTAL	28	100.00%

Hardly a contentious matter is the view regarding family income as a more reliable index of the family’s socio-economic status; it has a critical or profound influence on the personality development of adolescents and the psycho-affective dimension of their oral performance. This is, after all, undeniably bound up with the satisfaction of needs. Based on the results shown in both tables, the overall picture is not rosy. The monthly income of a great majority, 4999 and below to 5000-9999, places them at the borderline or below the poverty line. According to the latest National Statistics Office (*Umagang Kay Ganda*, ABS-CBN, April 2013), a monthly income below P7800 or so for a typical Filipino family of five is insufficient to ensure the family a decent life. A decent life means all the basic needs of the children (food, clothes, shelter, health and education) are taken care of. A low

income could mean privations that take their toll on the growth, personality development, and academic performance of adolescents.

There is congruence of the data on parents' monthly income and the data on educational attainment and occupation. Again, it must be noted that there are eleven college degree holders, but only half of these practice their professions; they find fulfillment in devoting all their time and effort to home and family. There are certainly implications of this home-centeredness for the education and personality growth of young children. The most relevant for this study are the ample opportunities for tapping the potential of the mother as a resource to the fullest, which Anderson (2000) proposes. Non-working mothers have the time to perform their role as primary caretakers. Although Anderson's article focused on the development of children's reading skills, her insistence on parental involvement applies to children's education or learning in general.

Appliances Found in the Home. Appliances found in the respondents' homes may have a bearing on the learning of young individuals, that is, as aids to learning. The presence of these makes for a supportive learning environment, while the lack of them indicates an impoverished environment. As shown in Table 5, the following learning-related appliances are found in the homes of the respondents: television, 26 (92.86%); radio/component, 19 (67.862%); computer system/laptop, 5 (17.86%); and tape recorder, 4 (14.297%).

Table 5. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Appliances Found in the Home*

Appliances at Home	Frequency	Percentage
Television	26	92.86%
Radio/component	19	67.86%
Rice cooker	17	60.71%
Refrigerator	12	42.86%
Washing machine	11	39.29%
Computer System/laptop	5	17.86%
Tape recorder	4	14.29%
Hair blower	1	3.57%

*Multiple Responses

Topping the list are television sets and radio/components, which provide media exposure to young learners, hence, relevant to the problem under study. Unfortunately, a computer system/laptop, a vital digital tool for learning, is lower down the list.

Like high-print homes (homes that are well-stocked with a variety of reading materials that motivate young learners to read, hence, acquisition-rich), homes furnished with appliances like a television set, a computer system/laptop, and a radio/component are associated with academic achievement; such an environment has a good chance of producing achievers. These media are a useful source of "comprehensible input" (Krashen, 1981) for language learning in this Age of Information Technology. Language learning is facilitated by the easy accessibility of exemplars or correct forms and modeling of the proper use of language (pronunciation, register/diction, etc.), for example, by program anchors, broadcasters and erudite or learned people who are featured in television shows. It has been observed that imitation, particularly of the phonological features of language, works well with young learners.

The home situation-school environment gap should not be so great as to cause students' culture shock and cause them disorientation. As Celce-Murcia (2000) stressed, media are so much a ubiquitous part of modern life (this is true even of rural areas that can be reached by electricity) that students would find it baffling if they do not find them in the home or in the school. Tomindug-Macarambon (2012) puts it this way in her thesis: "Indeed all this is far from a passing fad; notebooks, tablets, e-books and IPODs are clearly here to stay....What is clear is that the age of digital revolution

has dawned, and its repercussions or implications for the learning/education of the present generation are inevitable.”

In sum, socio-economic background or the social context in which students live, grow up and learn is a powerful factor influencing academic performance. Human behavior is inevitably shaped by the personal and environmental factors surrounding the individual. In the home where his parents, as his primary caretakers or earliest mentors, provide a secure and nurturing environment, his socialization and the molding of his personality, attitudes and values begin. Parents’ educational attainment, occupation and income are significant factors underpinning the nurture and development of the child (Eggen & Kauchak, 1999); cited in (Amer, 2013). Providing further support is McClelland’s work (cited in Tulaytay and Malawi, 2004), who underscored the importance of family circumstances for the need for learners’ achievement and performance. The quality and degree of intellectual stimulation and level of aspiration that parents exemplify would, to a considerable extent, determine the nurturance and development of this need.

3.2 Personality/ Character Types of the Respondent

Human behavior is influenced by personal and environmental factors surrounding the individual (Lewin, 1991; cited in Gregorio and Amer, 2013), and achievement, particularly learning, is a product or function of the interfaces between internal and external forces, as cited in Flores (2002). This time, attention is focused on respondents’ personality type or traits, which make up their internal climate.

To determine the personality/character types of the respondents, an adapted form of the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (1962; in Brown, 2000) was used. This personality inventory was developed based on the oft-quoted truism that every individual is unique and that he or she can capitalize on this uniqueness to succeed in any endeavor of his choice, for example, education or school. Borrowing from some of the original “types” analyzed by Carl Jung (1932), Myers and Briggs tested four dichotomous styles of functioning in their test, namely: introversion versus extroversion; sensing versus intuition; thinking versus feeling; and judging versus perceiving. Each of the four categories are capsulized in simple statement indicators. A five-point Likert Scale was used to determine type. How does it work? To illustrate, if a statement indicator for extroversion, for example, scores low on the scale, this can be interpreted as an inclination or propensity for introversion, and vice versa. For the sets of statement indicators for each category, see Appendix D. As illustrative samples, Tables 6.A (Extroversion and Introversion Personality/Character Types), 6.B (Intuition and Sensing Types), 6.C (Thinking and Feeling), and 6.D (Judging and Perceiving) are partially presented below. The other member of each pair is no longer shown.

Table 6.A. Extroversion vs Introversion Personality/Character Types

I-A Extroversion	(1) Never	(2) Seldom	(3) Sometimes	(4) Often	(5) Always
1) I enjoy mallng, eating out, and sightseeing with friends.	1 3.57%	3 10.71%	6 21.43%	11 39.29%	7 25.00%
2) I actively seek membership/ involvement in organizations, clubs, etc.	2 7.14%	1 3.57%	8 28.57%	11 39.29%	6 21.43%
3) In school, I go for collaborative learning.	5 17.86%	2 7.14%	13 46.43%	5 17.86%	3 10.71%
4) I like to play games with others.	2 7.14%	4 14.29%	11 39.29%	5 17.86%	6 21.43%
5) I’m a team player; I subordinate my interests to that of the group.	0 0.00%	1 3.57%	1 3.57%	8 28.57%	18 64.29%

*Multiple Responses

Based on the typing done, the following determinations were made: most of the respondents are extroverted; they go for outings with friends, working in groups, sharing and exchanging ideas, but shy away from activities that put them on the spot and involve risk-taking, such as performing in public. They are usually, not invariably or thoroughly, sensing rather than intuitive, describing themselves as data-oriented, down-to-earth, realistic and practical. They also revealed themselves as both thinking and feeling, depending on the situation, claiming to have tendencies to be objective, impartial and analytic, but at the same time also tend to be subjective, intimacy-seeking and have the capacity for warmth and sympathy. They are more inclined to be judging than perceiving, that is, engage in planning, tend to meet problems head-on, and prefer to be in control.

A demonstration of how determinations were made regarding the stronger tendency to extroversion than to introversion is in order, or justifiable, because of the four pairs of categories, these types have the more pronounced bearing on the psycho-affective dimension of oral performance. Statement indicators Nos. 5 "I am a team player; I subordinate my interests to that of the group", (64.29%); No. 7 "I delight in conversations, discussions, and exchange or sharing of ideas", (53.57%) and No. 1 "I enjoy malling, eating out, and sight-seeing with friends" (25.00%) rank 1st, 2nd and 3rd in terms of frequency, rated by most respondents as *always* practiced or manifested. Another large group rated the same items as *often* engaged in or manifested.

Statement indicator Nos. 6 ("I love performing before a crowd in public") and 8 (Friends/Others seek my company") rank the lowest in terms of frequency - 7.14% both for *always*. Also described as *always* practiced or manifested are Nos. 2 ("I actively seek membership/involvement in organizations, clubs, etc.") and 4 ("I like to play games with others"). At the lower end, labeled *never*, indicators Nos. 6 ("I love performing before a crowd in public") and 3 ("In school, I go for collaborative and cooperative learning") stand out with frequency 35.71% and 17.86%, respectively.

In regard the type Introversion, statement indicators Nos. 5 ("I do not bother listening to other people's problems"), 3 ("I retreat to isolated, quiet places because I hate company"), and 4 ("I would rather read curled up in bed than join other family members in an activity", with frequencies 50.00%, 25.00%, and 17.86%, respectively, rank 1st, 2nd and 3rd. described as *always* done. Often, indicators Nos. 3 ("I retreat to isolated, quiet places because I hate company"), 4 ("I would rather read curled up in bed than join other family members in an activity") and 1 ("I prefer working alone to working with others") record the highest frequencies - 39.29%, 35.71% and 32.14%, respectively. Identified under *never* as leading the list in terms of frequency are the following: Nos. 7 ("I do not have a best friend"), 75.00%; 2 ("I don't self-disclose or talk about my problems; I keep them to myself"), 46.43%; and 1 ("I prefer working alone to working with others"), 21.43%.

Comparison of the frequencies recorded in Tables 6-A and 6-B shows that the tendency to extroversion is stronger than the tendency to introversion, as in the study of Cruda-Berowa (2012). The majority manifest positive or desirable social traits, specifically a desire for company, working, doing or performing tasks with others, teamwork and subordinating one's interests to those of the group, forging relationships/friendship, and communicating/interacting/sharing with others. Generally, the respondents are inclined to reach out beyond the self to others. However, there is also admission or recognition of negative tendencies like apathy or indifference to others' problems, a preference for isolating oneself and hating the company, and working alone.

Even in SLA or ESL instructional material development and evaluation, Tomlinson (1998; 2005, 2007) need for attention to the affective aspect: "Materials should take into account that learners differ in affective attitudes...and therefore, should offer variety (Wenden & Rubin, 1987). Other relevant guiding principles are relaxed learning (helping learners feel at ease and gain confidence) and maximizing learning potential by encouraging not only intellectual, but also emotional involvement

by stimulating both right and left brain activities, and achieving affective engagement (Tomlinson, 2005; 2007).

The significance of personality type/traits for the learning process, particularly oral performance, is given special emphasis in Schumann's Acculturation Model (1978) with its constellations of social and psychological or affective variables. As asserted by him, even if the social conditions are favorable or conducive to language acquisition, if the psychological-affective variables militate against it, language learning may not be as effective, or it may not even happen; unfavorable social circumstances may be overcome by learners whose predispositions and attitudes are strongly positive. All four variables belonging to this particular network of variables – i.e., language ego, culture shock, ego permeability, and motivation – have their equivalents in this study. For example, language ego, which is the fear of ridicule from appearing comical when struggling to use another language, is treated as a lack of confidence, low self-esteem, or high affective filter in this paper. With a language ego grown rigid, a person is less open or receptive to new stimuli and influences that come with exposure to the second language. This condition is comparable or even akin to having a high affective filter (Krashen, 1981; 1982). It is also closely related to inhibition.

On the other hand, individuals whose language egos are still permeable have a better chance of succeeding in learning a second language. Evidence favoring this view is derived from research with adult subjects in whom temporary states of lowered inhibition were induced through hypnosis or consumption of alcohol, and who then displayed somewhat improved pronunciation in a second or foreign language. Schumann seized this finding regarding the effect of a lowered inhibition and related it to a learner's openness to target language input (1986).

Relative to the foregoing, compelling attention is many respondents' tendency to shy away from practices or activities that involve risk-taking through self-exposure, such as performing before a crowd in public, playing games with others, self-disclosing or talking about personal problems, and just keeping these to themselves. These reveal inhibition, earlier defined as defensiveness against new experiences and feelings to protect the ego and anxiety. The process of building defenses, begun in childhood, continues into adolescence and adulthood. Individuals with higher self-esteem and ego strength can withstand threats to their self-esteem and ego, and thus have lower defenses. Those with weaker self-esteem erect walls of inhibition or defensive barriers to protect their weak or fragile ego, and thus show a lack of self-confidence in a situation or task (Brown, 1994, 2000). Finally, motivation in Schumann's model is also motivation in this study – an inner force or drive -- which lends itself to classification as integrative or instrumental, and as extrinsic or intrinsic.

To sum up, the relevance of personality type/traits to second language learning, particularly oral performance, which is the primary focus of interest of this inquiry, can hardly be overemphasized. As shown in the analysis of data on the first category, the Extroversion-Introversion dichotomy, only the potential or possible effect of these opposed types has a link with second language learning. Erhman (1989), in his study, for example, underscored an important trait manifested by extroverts in relation to language learning: a willingness to take conversational risks. On the other hand, considered as plus factors or assets in the case of introverts, are concentration and self-sufficiency. Generally, extroverts are social animals that set up few defensive barriers and tend to take risks; in other words, without high ego boundaries to hold them back, they show aggressiveness and self-assertion. This tendency should be helpful in oral performance.

However, there are also major liabilities observed in extroverts and introverts (Ehrman, 1989). Extroverts tend to be dependent on outside stimulation and interaction. At the same time, introverts need to process ideas before speaking sometimes, and this cautiousness can sometimes lead to avoidance of linguistic risks in conversation. It is said that to be able to learn, one must not be afraid to make mistakes. Errors or mistakes, as pointed out in the studies on error analysis, Khalid-Masorong

(2010) and Ulla (2012), are now seen in a kinder light and should not be dreaded or avoided as one would the plague. Errors should work *for*, not *against*, students.

3.3 Respondents' Performance on the Oral Test (Oral Performance)

Table 7 below presents the four (4) broad categories or measures that served as guidelines for the Board of Raters in the assessment of the oral performance of the respondents: *Language*, *Vitality* (Vocal Appeal), *Visual Appeal*, and *Audience Appeal*.

Table 7. Respondents' Oral/Speech Development (Assessed by a Board of Raters)

Speech Development	Very Low Mastery	Average Mastery	Moving Towards Mastery	Mastered
I. Purpose	1	2	3	4
B. Language				0
1) Vivid	10 35.71%	16 57.14%	2 7.14%	0 0.00%
2) Effective Usage	16 57.14%	11 39.29%	1 3.57%	0 0.00%
II. Vitality				
A. Vocal Appeal				
1) Quality	1 3.57%	11 39.29%	2 7.14%	0 0.00%
2) Pitch	11 39.29%	1 3.57%	2 7.14%	0 0.00%
3) Loudness	14 50.00%	10 35.71%	3 10.71%	1 3.57%
4) Control	18 64.29%	9 32.14%	1 3.57%	0 0.00%
5) Rhythm	10 35.71%	18 64.29%	0 0.00%	0 0.00%
6) Phrasing	6 21.43%	21 75.00%	1 3.57%	0 0.00%

Language is used in the sense of rhetoric which involves the exploitation of the verbal possibilities or resources of language. It is concerned with the effective use of diction, figures of speech, rhetorical devices and effects, and other stylistic features, such as sentence or syntactic patterns and rhythmic patterns. Vividness and effectiveness were rated.

Table 7.1. Results/Score on Language

Speech Development	Very Low Mastery	Average Mastery	Moving Towards Mastery	Mastery
1. Purpose	1	2	3	4
Language				
2. Vividness	10 35.71%	16 57.14%	2 7.14%	0 0.0%
3. Effective Usage	16 57.14%	11 39.29%	1 3.5%	0 0.00%

The results are as follows: *vividness* (average, 57.14%; very low mastery, 35.00%) and *effective usage* (average, 39.29%; very low mastery, 57.14%). The respondents scored better on vividness than on effective usage.

Vitality or *Vocal Appeal* is equivalent to *pronunciato*, which is the fifth in the *Canons* of Cicero. This refers to delivery in English. However, as the qualities measured indicate, vitality here denotes, or is limited to, the audio or auditory aspect of delivery. The measures or qualities rated under *Vocal Appeal* are quality, pitch, loudness, control, rhythm, phrasing, articulation and pronunciation.

Table 7.2. Results/Scores on Vitality (Vocal Appeal)

Vocal Appeal	Very Low	Average	Moving Towards	Mastery
	Mastery	Mastery	Mastery	Mastery
	1	2	3	4
1. Quality	15 53.57%	11 39.29%	2 7.14%	0 0.0%
2. Pitch	11 39.29%	16 57.14%	2 7.14%	0 0.0%
3. Loudness	14 50.00%	10 35.71%	3 10.71%	0 0.00%
4. Control	18 64.29%	9 32.14%	1 3.5%	0 0.0%
5. Rhythm	10 35.71%	18 64.29%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%
6. Phrasing	6 21.43%	21 75.00%	1 3.5%	0 0.0%
7. Articulation & Pronunciation	7 25.00%	19 67.86%	2 7.14%	0 0.0%

Larger groups of respondents are concentrated in the lower two levels of the scale, *Very Low Mastery* and *Average Mastery*. On phrasing (75%), pronunciation and articulation (67.86%), and rhythm (64.29%), they were rated *Average*. On control (64.29%), quality (53.57%), and loudness (50.00%), they did not fare as well. The overall rating is *Very Low*.

The rest of the results are: *pitch* (average, 3.57%; very low mastery, 39.29%); *rhythm* (average, 64.29%; very low mastery, 35.71%); *phrasing* (average, 75.00; very low mastery, 21.43%); *articulation and pronunciation* (average, 67.86%; very low mastery, 27.00%).

Visual Appeal refers to the visual aspect of delivery. This covers the non-verbal means or natural accompaniments to speech: kinesics or facial expression, gestures, posture, stance or comportment on stage, and the like.

Table 8. Oral/Speech Development Vitality (B. Visual Appeal)

Vocal Appeal	Very Low	Average	Moving Towards	Mastery
	Mastery	Mastery	Mastery	Mastery
	1	2	3	4
1. Posture & Poise	14 50.00%	14 50.00%	0 0.00%	0 0.0%
2. Gesture & Mannerism	21 75.00%	6 21.43%	1 3.5%	0 0.0%
3. Facial Expression	23 82.14%	4 14.29%	1 3.5%	0 0.00%
4. Platform Technique	21 75.00%	7 25.00%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%

Results for the measures or qualities rated are: *posture and poise* (average, 50.00%; very low mastery, 50.00%); *gesture and mannerisms* (average, 21.43%; very low mastery, 75.00%); *facial expression*

(average, 14.29%; very low mastery, 82,14%; *platform technique* (average, 25.00%; very low mastery, 75.00%). Crowding or clustering of respondents in the lowest level, *Very Low*, is immediately riveting.

The overall result of the Oral Presentation is *Very Low*, pointing up the need for a critical examination to discover the locus of the problem.

3.4 Psycho-Affective Factors with Facilitative and Debilitative Effects on Respondents'

Oral Production/Performance. This section examines psycho-affective factors that are assumed to have a possible facilitative or debilitating effect on the respondents' oral performance. These factors, comprising the intervening variables -- anxiety, motivation and self-esteem -- were deliberately singled out by the researcher from a list of psycho-affective factors for consideration in this inquiry.

Table 9.A presents the students' responses to statement indicators that reveal the occurrence of anxiety.

Table 9.A. Respondents' Response on Occurrence of Anxiety*

Statement	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
1. During oral recitations, I feel nervous thinking that I might fail to answer the question.	0 0.00%	5 17.86%	4 14.29%	17 60.71%	2 7.14%
2. I usually place myself nearer to the side than in the center of the room.	0 0.00%	7 25.00%	5 17.86%	8 28.57%	8 28.57%
3. I sweat easily even in cold days, especially when I must deliver my report in front of the class.	2 7.14%	7 25.00%	8 28.57%	11 39.29%	0 0.00%
4. Experience twitching, trembling or shaky feelings.	0 0.00%	3 10.71%	2 7.14%	18 64.29%	5 17.86%
5. I feel highly anxious and self-conscious all the time.	0 0.00%	5 17.86%	8 28.57%	15 53.57%	0 0.00%
6. I get numbness and/or tingling feeling in my extremities (i.e. hands, feet, etc.)	0 0.00%	5 17.86%	6 21.43%	10 35.71%	7 25.00%
7. I feel nervous when I am in front of my classmates and teacher, I could not speak a word.	0 0.00%	4 14.29%	8 28.57%	15 53.57%	1 3.57%
8. I can relax when I am in front of my teacher and classmates.	0 0.00%	9 32.14%	10 35.71%	8 28.57%	1 3.57%
9. I feel comfortable in speaking in front of a crowd.	1 3.57%	6 21.43%	6 21.43%	7 25.00%	8 28.57%
10. I have dry mouth when I am about to speak.	2 7.14%	8 28.57%	5 17.86%	13 46.43	0 0.00%

Revealed here is the vulnerability of the majority of the respondents to anxiety and related feelings like apprehension, tension and nervousness. Under the column Strongly Agree, relatively few, and in smaller percentages, admitted experiencing the following: No. 2 ("I usually place myself nearer to the side than in the center of the room"), 28.37%; No. 6 ("I get numbness and/or tingling feeling in my extremities. . ."), 25.00%; and No. 4 ("Experience twitching, trembling or shaky feelings"). However, under the Agree column, there is clustering of larger numbers of the respondents about certain indicators: No. 4 ("Experience twitching, trembling or shaky feelings"), 64.21%; No.1 ("During oral recitations, I feel nervous thinking that I might fail to answer the question"), 60.71%;

No.5 (“I feel highly nervous and self-conscious all the time”), 53.57%; No.7 (“I feel nervous when I am in front of my classmates and teachers; I could not speak a word”), 53.57%; No. 10 (“I have a dry mouth when I am about to speak”), 40.43%; and No.3 (“I sweat easily when I have to deliver my report in front of the class”), 39.29%.

It is clear from the disclosures above that anxiety is common among students, particularly in situations involving performance like recitation, reporting, or doing something in front of the class or teacher. They develop cold feet and dry mouth, or experience numbness, twitching, trembling, tingling sensations, and profuse sweating. These are all symptomatic of an anxiety attack and the accompanying nervousness, which students typically experience in the learning context. Having to perform in a second or a foreign language compounds the apprehension.

The situational nature of the state type of anxiety has been the focus of interest of recent studies on foreign language anxiety. Three components of foreign language anxiety have been identified (Horwitz et al., 1986; MacIntyre and Gardner, 1989, 1991): communication apprehension, arising from learners’ inability to adequately express mature thoughts and ideas; fear of negative evaluation; and test anxiety or anxiety over academic evaluation. Studies inspired by MacIntyre and Gardner and others after them, like Young (1991) and Phillips (1992), conclude that “foreign language anxiety can be distinguished from other types of anxiety and that it can hurt the language learning process” (MacIntyre & Gardner, 1991).

Aside from the global-state/situational distinction, distinction is also made between facilitative and debilitating anxiety (Alpert and Haber, 1960, cited in Scovel, 1978). Not all forms of anxiety should be treated as a kind of plague that must be avoided at all costs. Feelings of “test anxiety” before an examination (Madsen, 1982; Phillips, 1992) are all too familiar. This is an example of a state anxiety as it is situational in nature. The notion of facilitative anxiety suggests that some apprehension or tension over a task to be accomplished is actually a positive factor. Otherwise, overconfidence might result in mediocre results. A little facilitative tension that keeps one poised, alert and just slightly unbalanced to the point that one cannot relax entirely is needed. The slight feeling of nervousness before a public performance is, in experienced speakers, a sign of facilitative anxiety, just enough tension to get the job done.

In Rogers’ humanistic theory of learning, just enough anxiety and a nondefensive posture receive emphasis as a source of motivation or stimulation. Recognizing how anxiety can cause learners to feel defensive, thus blocking learning, language educators and researchers in the field have developed methodologies that make the learning environment as embracing, warm, comfortable and reassuring as possible, and reduce tension and apprehension -- the so-called designers’ methods in the seventies, such as the Silent Way of Gattegno and Suggestopedia of Lozanov. Those methods make much of the importance of a supportive, nonthreatening environment. Crookall and Oxford (1991) suggest that the classroom become a place of warmth and friendliness, where competitiveness is de-emphasized, risk-taking is rewarded and encouraged, and peer work, small group work, games and simulations are featured. Student-to-student interaction, as in brainstorming, is also promoted. Such techniques or activities, which involve less apprehension, have been tried to train students to deal with anxiety directly.

On the other hand, the ability to take risks may be facilitative of second language acquisition/learning. Not a few researchers, like Bailey (1983), believe that learners who are willing to take risks by guessing at meaning, or have a high tolerance for ambiguity and uncertainty, develop language skills more rapidly than their more inhibited peers. Facilitative anxiety, which consists of some apprehension over a task to be done, is a positive factor; it is, in fact, one of the keys to success. It is distinguished from debilitating anxiety (also cited in Scovel, 1978; in Brown, 1994, 2004), which is an extreme form of nervous tension that is paralyzing, as the word suggests, and hinders the process

of language learning. The trick, according to Bailey, is to “find that optimal point along the continuum” of the construct.

The respondents’ responses on the second psycho-affective factor, motivation, are set out in Table 9.B.

Table 9.B. Respondents’ Responses on Motivation*

Statement	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
1) It is in my nature to assume responsibility in my English class especially in oral activities.	2 7.14%	3 10.71%	1 3.57%	12 42.86%	10 35.71%
2) When I am feeling down, I remind myself to focus on the good things, no matter how minor.	0 0.00%	2 7.14%	3 10.71%	15 53.57%	8 28.57%
3) I feel unhappy if I cannot answer the questions correctly during oral recitations.	1 3.57%	4 14.29%	1 3.57%	6 21.43%	16 57.14%
4) I feel bored if I must do oral activities.	7 25.00%	4 14.29%	6 21.43%	6 21.43%	5 17.86%
5) I do not care if I cannot answer all the questions during oral recitation.	17 60.71%	6 21.43%	2 7.14%	3 10.71%	0 0.00%
6) I strive hard in my English class especially in learning oral communication to meet my goals.	1 3.57%	1 3.57%	4 14.29%	10 35.71%	12 42.86%
7) I engage myself in oral recitation in my English class.	2 7.14%	3 10.71%	2 7.14%	19 67.86%	2 7.14%
8) I am not good in speaking but it is not an excuse for met to stop learning it.	0 0.00%	0 0.00%	3 10.71%	10 35.71%	15 53.57%
9) I like my English subject because it is my way of improving my speaking/oral skill.	0 0.00%	0 0.00%	0 0.00%	5 17.86%	23 82.14%
10) I am always motivated to do my report given by our teachers.	0 0.00%	0 0.00%	1 3.57%	14 50.00%	13 46.43%

*Multiple Response

The respondents strongly agree on the following: No. 9 (“I like my English subject because it is my way of improving my speaking/oral skill”), 82.14%; No.3 (“I feel unhappy if I cannot answer the questions correctly during oral recitations”), 57.14%; No.8 (“I am not good in speaking but it is not an excuse for me to stop learning it”), 53.57%; No. 10 (“I am always motivated to do report given by the teachers”), 46.43%; No. 6 (“I strive hard in my English class especially in learning oral communication to meet my goals”), 42.86%; and No. 1 (“It is in my nature to assume responsibility in my English class, especially in oral activities”), 35.71%.

Large groups agree on the following motivation indicators: No. 7 (“I engage myself in oral recitation in my English class”), 67.86%; No. 10 (“I am always motivated to do report given by our teachers”), 50.00%; No.2 (“When I am feeling down, I remind myself to focus on the good. . .”), 53.57; and No.1 (“It is my nature to assume responsibility in my English class, especially in oral activities”), 42.86%.

As can be gleaned from the respondents’ answers, motivation is indeed an inner drive or desire that moves the individual to a particular action, causes one to act in a certain way, or propels

him/her towards a goal. Also, based on the leading indicators above, a great majority of the respondents, if not all, are intrinsically motivated. As described by Deci (1975), “intrinsically motivated behaviors are aimed at bringing about certain internally rewarding consequences, namely, feelings of competence and self-determination.” The result provides validation or confirmation of the findings of numerous studies that, given proper motivation, particularly intrinsic motivation, learners find learning facilitated and success easier to realize. The respondents in this study draw strength or inspiration from within. They see learning the language as a responsibility and a need. In fact, a large number, forming a huge proportion, 82.14%, admit liking the English subject “because it is a way of improving my speaking/oral skills.”

Intrinsic motivation is heavily favored by familiar names like Bruner, Crookes and Schmidt (1991), and Brown (1990), who believe that it works more for long-term retention. Piaget and others have pointed out that human beings view incongruity, uncertainty and “disequilibrium” as motivating or stimulating. They believe that learners seek out a reasonable challenge and are stimulated by some apprehension or tension. In the face of a challenge, the learner initiates behaviors intended to overcome or conquer the challenging situation. As explained by Krashen (1985; in Brown, 1994, 2000), incongruity is not itself motivating, but rather optimal incongruity, which is represented by the formula $i + 1$ (comprehensible input), which presents just enough challenge and the possibility of being resolved.

Table 9.C. Respondents’ Responses on Self Esteem*

Statement	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
1) I hate myself because every time we have assigned report and activities in English, I feel so shy. I feel that I am not good at all in speaking.	4 14.29%	9 32.14%	5 17.86%	5 17.86%	1 3.57%
2) I lose control of myself when speaking in front of the class.	4 14.29%	11 39.29%	7 25.00%	5 17.86%	1 3.57%
3) When I am speaking in front of a crowd I tend to postpone speaking because I cannot speak directly or spontaneously.	5 17.86%	10 35.71%	4 14.29%	9 32.14%	0 0.00%
4) I feel I do not have much to be proud of since I am not a good speaker of the English language.	5 17.86%	18 64.29%	2 7.14%	2 7.14%	1 3.57%
5) My muscles are tense when I speak in front and sometimes, I perspire a great deal.	2 7.14%	6 21.43%	7 25.00%	12 42.86%	1 3.57%
6) I sometimes cannot express my ideas in class as all eyes are looking at me and my tongue is tied or twisted.	0 0.00%	5 17.86%	3 10.71%	19 67.86%	1 3.57%
7) I consider speaking/oral activity difficult than the other macro skills like writing, listening, and reading.	1 3.57%	5 17.86%	2 7.14%	17 60.71%	3 10.71%
8) I enjoy the challenge of question-and-answer portion during my report.	0 0.00%	4 14.29%	6 21.43%	9 32.14%	9 32.14%
9) I am usually the first to react to questions that are raised in class.	0 0.00%	5 17.86%	7 25.00%	12 42.86%	4 14.29%
10) I feel that I have a number of good qualities that enable me to speak the English language.	0 0.00%	2 7.14%	5 17.86%	16 57.14%	5 17.86%

As shown in Table 9.C, self-esteem indicators that are negatively couched or worded were described as strongly agree by fewer respondents which comprise negligible percentages, as the following illustrate: No.3 (“When I am speaking in front of a crowd, I tend to postpone speaking because I cannot speak directly or spontaneously”), 0.00%; No. 1 (“I hate myself because every time we have assigned reports and activities in English, I feel so shy; I feel that I am not good at all in speaking”), 3.57%; No. 2 (“I lose control of myself when speaking in front of the class”), 3.57%; No. 4 (“I feel I do not have much to be proud of since I am not a good speaker of the English language”), 3.57%; No.5 (“My muscles are tense when I speak in front and sometimes I perspire a great deal”), 3.57%; and No. 6 (“I sometimes cannot express my ideas in class as all eyes are looking at me and my tongue is tied and twisted”), 3.57%.

In contrast, indicators that are positively stated were affirmed by larger numbers: No. 8 (“I enjoy the challenges of question-and-answer portion during my report”), 32.29%; No. 10 (“I feel that I have a number of good qualities that enable me to speak in the English language”), 17.86%; No.9 (“I am usually the first to react to questions that are raised in class”), 14.29%; and No. 7 (“I consider speaking/oral activity difficult than the other macro skills. . .”), 10.71%.

Larger groups/percentages acknowledged only agreeing on the following negatively stated indicators: No. 6 (“I sometimes cannot express my ideas in class as all eyes are looking at me, and my tongue is tied and twisted”), 67.86%; No.5 (“My muscles are tense when I speak in front and sometimes I perspire a great deal”), 42.85%; and No.1 (“I hate myself because every time we have assigned reports and activities in English, I feel shy. . .”), 32.14%. Among the positively stated indicators, the top three in the agree column are: No 7 (“I consider speaking/oral activity difficult than other macro skills. . .”), 60.71%; No. 10 (“I feel that I have a number of good qualities that make me speak the English language”), 57.18%; and No. 9 (“I am usually the first to react to questions raised in school”), 42.86%.

As revealing is the result for the strongly disagree column. No respondent owned up to being describable by the following indicators: No.6 (“I sometimes cannot express my ideas in class as all eyes are looking at me and my tongue is tied and twisted”); No. 8 (“I enjoy the challenge of question-and-answer portion during my report”); No.9 (“I am usually the first to react to questions that are raised in class”); and No. 10 (“I feel that I have several good qualities that enable me to speak the English language. Except for No. 6, the rest in this set of statement indicators can be considered disclaimers, or, as the researcher interprets them, either a display of false modesty or a confession of lack of self-esteem and self-confidence.

Clearly, speaking/oral performance is found by a majority of the respondents as more difficult than the other macro skills. Signs of nervousness or apprehension are named by them: self-consciousness; tongue-tied, timidity or shyness, tense muscles, perspiring a great deal, and the like. On the other hand, some claimed to “enjoy the challenge of the question-and-answer portion during report” and “usually the first to react to questions raised in class.”

It is a truism that no activity, whether cognitive or affective, can be carried out and pursued to its triumphant conclusion without some measure of self-esteem, self-confidence, knowledge of oneself, and belief in one’s capabilities to undertake that activity and carry it through to completion. As defined by Coopersmith (1967), self-esteem is “the evaluation which the individual makes and maintains about himself. It expresses an attitude of approval or disapproval, and indicates the extent to which an individual believes himself to be capable, significant, successful and worthy. In short, self-esteem is a personal judgment of worthiness that is expressed in the attitudes that the individual holds towards himself.” Gardner and Lambert (1972), Brodkey and Shore (1976), and Watkins et al. (1991) assert that it is a pivotal variable in second language learning, based on evidence provided by numerous studies.

Like the result for the anxiety occurrence and level, the result for self-esteem illustrates specific and task aspects of self-esteem. Most respondents have a common fear or dread of oral activity/performance. Having to speak, recite or deliver a report puts them on the defensive, which

reveals their language ego or fear of ridicule (Schumann, 1978) and high affective filter. The Affective Filter Hypothesis formulated by Krashen (1982) links the process of language acquisition/ learning with anxiety, motivation and self-confidence. Learners with already rigid language ego and “high or strong” filters are unable to use all available input because psychological factors as those mentioned, interfere. On the other hand, those with “lower or weaker” affective filters shaped by lower anxiety, high self-esteem and self-confidence, and stronger motivation, are likely to take advantage of learning opportunities and be more open to using these.

Many respondents frankly declared not being good at all in speaking English, referring to certain difficulties like being unable to speak directly or spontaneously, and expressing one’s ideas in class, feeling shy and nervous. Adelaide Heyde (1979; cited in Brown, 1994, 2000) studied the effects of the three levels of self-esteem on performance of an oral production task by American college students learning French as a foreign language, and found that all three correlated positively with performance on the oral production measures; the highest correlation was discovered to be between task self-esteem and performance.

To recapitulate, the psycho-affective factors motivation and self-esteem are essential factors in oral performance, which many students consider as a “trying,” thus a dreaded experience. Self-confidence, self-esteem and stronger motivation have a facilitative effect on oral performance; these work as boosters. Regarding anxiety, which is often considered a negative factor and should be avoided at all costs like the plague, it has been shown in numerous studies as that of Alpert and Haber (1960; cited in Scovel, 1978), that there is a need to modify this original concept of anxiety. Some measure of anxiety (in the form of concern or apprehension over a task to be done) has, in fact, a facilitative effect on performance. Indifference or a “so-so” attitude may, in fact, be damaging. It is facilitative tension that keeps one poised, alert and just slightly nervous or tense.

Thus far, psycho-affective factors, specifically motivation and self-esteem, that have a facilitative effect on oral production/performance have been identified. Anxiety manifested by physical signs like profuse perspiration, trembling, twitching, and going tongue-tied and feelings like nervousness are commonly recognized as negative factors, but as argued in other studies, can work to the advantage of the learner. Some measure of anxiety can generate facilitative tension that keeps one poised, alert, focused and even more resolute to do good. Regarding factors that have a debilitating effect on oral performance, the answer to the question is the obverse of the same three psycho-affective factors – i.e., anxiety, motivation and self-esteem – examined in the previous analysis. Data on this are also contained in Table Nos. 9-A, 9-B, and 9-C.

Actually, of the three intervening factors, anxiety stands out for having a facilitative and debilitating potential as a factor to consider in oral performance; in other words, too much of it can have an inhibitory, paralyzing or debilitating effect, but just enough of it can have a facilitative effect. Anxiety can therefore work *for* or *against* the learner. As already explained, a slight degree or level of anxiety or active anticipation keeps one alert, poised and not entirely relaxed or overconfident to get something done, and in the process, avoid turning in a sloppy or mediocre, haphazardly done, or “wishy-washy” performance. On the other hand, extreme anxiety can be debilitating or paralyzing, thus blocking learning or totally ruining one’s oral performance. Manifestations or signs of debilitating anxiety are found in Table 9-A: twitching and trembling or tremors (No.4), 64.29%; self-consciousness (No.5), 53.57%; inability/difficulty speaking in front of classmates (No. 7), 53.57%; dry mouth (No. 10), 46.43%; sweating profusely when reporting, even on a cold day (No.3), 39.29%; feeling of numbness, tingling sensation (No.6), 35.71%; nervousness during oral recitations and fear of failing to answer questions (No.1), 32.14%. All these are associated with apprehension, nervousness, and tension, which accompany debilitating anxiety. Any one of these, or a combination of two or three, could block or spoil one’s oral performance. The occurrence of such feelings signals a high or strong affective filter (Krashen, 1982).

In Krashen's model of second language acquisition, the affective filter plays a crucial mediating role: it determines whether or not the learner will seek and be able to take advantage of acquisition opportunities, that is, of available input. If the learner is anxious, apprehensive, and overly tense, acquisition/learning will be hindered and blocked. No learning occurs. Obviously, extreme anxiety can be disabling.

No one is likely to refute the claim made for motivation as a *sine qua non* or indispensable ingredient of success in any endeavor, or a key to learning. It necessarily follows that a lack of motivation spells failure or poor performance. Only two signs of lack of motivation are named in Table 9-B: boredom (No.4), 21.43% and indifference or not caring whether one can answer all the questions during oral recitation (No.5), 10.71%. Lack of interest or motivation, which boredom and indifference or a "could not care less" attitude proclaim in the same way that yawning or restlessness and inattentiveness do, douses all enthusiasm for learning, and along with it, all desire to participate and be engaged in acquisition activities like oral performance. To learn, humans need to be active - to explore, manipulate, acquire knowledge, and enhance the ego.

Table 9-C lists some manifestations of debilitating lack of self-esteem, which include the following: extreme shyness accompanied by the feeling of inadequacy (that one is not good enough in speaking (No.1), 32.14%; loss of control when speaking in front of the class, which betrays nervousness, tension or lack of confidence (No. 2), 17.86%; tendency to take much time to speak before an audience or crowd and inability to speak spontaneously (No.3), 32.14%; lack of self-confidence/belief in oneself (No.4). 7.14%; tensed muscles and profuse perspiration when speaking (No.5), 42.86%; inability to express ideas and getting tongue-tied (No. 6), 67.86%; and finding speaking more difficult than other skills (No 7), 60.71%.

The last two indicators suggest conditioning or convincing of the self that one "cannot do it," which reveals a lack of self-esteem and self-confidence, or a negative image of self. This defeatist or negative attitude dooms all efforts to futility, or might even translate into the learner not even making an effort at all, because as his/her argument goes, he/she cannot express his/her ideas, and finds speaking/oral activity more difficult than the other macro skills. It betrays low self-esteem, lack of confidence, and faith in oneself. A student who thinks this way already puts a roadblock to learning or oral performance. He develops a bias against, or even hostility, towards speaking, specifically oral production or performance. The enormous pressure to which oral performance subjects him is unbearable. He concedes defeat even before trying; in other words, the lack of self-esteem demonstrated is disabling.

4.0 Conclusion

The study's findings bring to the surface the serious learning problem of the respondents, a group of third-year students comprising two sections. The results do not augur well for effective language learning, especially the development of oral skills in English as a second language, which is a requisite for college work, that is, for those aspiring to proceed to tertiary education. Social and psycho-affective factors seem to be hostile or inhospitable to and conspire against effective language learning. The problem is compounded by the observed seeming lack of realization on the part of teachers that learning potential can be maximized by encouraging intellectual or cognitive and affective involvement. Less attention is paid to creating a supportive, dynamic, non-threatening and nurturing learning environment. Teaching is limited to the mechanical execution of the lesson plan and assessment. Apparently, teachers lack awareness or appreciation of the fact that learning in a second language is fraught with difficulty, and that learning, particularly language learning, is fundamentally affective and interpersonal.

The odds are not exactly insurmountable, or the problems insoluble, since the respondents still had one-and-a-half years to benefit from an intervention program designed for remediation of

their language learning difficulties. Such an initiative can be worked out only through the collective or concerted effort of teachers, the school administration and parents. All sectors must be involved in the creation of a supportive learning environment.

The respondents' personal data reveal that most of the residents came from disadvantaged or low medium-income families, and although many have a television set and radio/component at home, a computer as a learning tool is rarely among the household appliances. Based on the Personality/Character typing, the respondents are mostly extroverted; however, early on, many admitted their aversion to performing in public. This foreshadows the result of the Oral Presentation; the overall rating for performance in said class activity was *Low to Very Low*. Honest reporting dictates that it be stated here that of the original 55-man sample or number of participants, only 28 stayed to participate in the Oral Presentation. Almost half, twenty-seven (27), took flight despite the efforts of both teachers and the researcher to stop them from leaving the classroom. On learning that a Board of Raters would evaluate their performance, those respondents panicked. This behavior served as proof of the students' vulnerability to anxiety, particularly in such contexts as performing in public. Of the three intervening variables – anxiety, motivation and self-esteem, anxiety due to fear of public performance, especially in a second or foreign language, drew a common reaction/response. Their escape from the Oral Presentation is, in fact, a testimony to the school's failure to help cultivate confidence and self-esteem in students.

Taking cognizance of the serious learning problems of students in rural areas, with oral performance/production in English as a Second Language, the researcher as a teacher herself, and grateful for the cooperation of the study's respondents and their teachers, offers the following recommendation: a) for teachers, seminar-workshops on teaching methods, techniques and activities (featuring teaching demos) that create a non-threatening or supportive and embracing learning environment; sensitivity training program that includes lectures and exercises on humanistic pedagogy (Carl Rogers) that shifts attention from teaching to learning, from the cognitive to the affective dimension of learning, and treats the learner as a "whole person", that is, not only a thinking but also a feeling person; experiential and task-based learning that develop critical thinking; and new perspectives and teaching strategies or programs such as those of Brazilian educator Paulo Freire; and sustained "Mentoring the Mentor" sessions –sharing of more engaging or stimulating teaching techniques and a rich variety of tasks or activities organized by teachers themselves and supported by the school administration; b) for students, free tutorials (individual or in groups) after class or during the weekend and peer tutoring or some forms of cooperative learning to encourage more interactions between students and help them overcome self-consciousness, nervousness and anxiety when performing in class.

5.0 Generalizability of Findings

The findings of this inquiry are believed to be generalizable not only to high school students in all other public high schools within the purview of the Mindanao State University, but considerably more to those under the supervision of the DepEd, given similar circumstances in which these schools operate – i.e. rural setting, socio-economic conditions, administrative/management problems, congestion, questionable staffing and hiring practices (especially of teachers), lack of learning tools, lack of exposure for both teachers and students, etc. The problems obtaining in these "learning spaces" are legion and chronic and may vary only in terms of degree or gravity. Said problems are decreed to the point of stridency, in numerous studies made by researchers and graduate students (for their theses or dissertations). The need for reform in the educational system is a moral clarion call not only for school administrations/leaders, but also for policy makers, the local government officials, parents and the entire community. Providing quality education to the youth is, after all, everybody's business.

6.0 Conflict of Interest

As the sole author of the entire study, the researcher declares no conflict of interest related to the research. The following were ensured: that her study was original and not a duplication of any previous studies; that the same met the requirements and standards of the approving Department and Graduate School; and that the inquiry was carried out in accordance with ethical research principles and practices.

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